

BRIDGING GENDER GAP IN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH: ELIMINATING THE BARRIERS AND SUSTAINING THE ENABLERS

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Key Messages

- The WESTIR project provides valuable insights into the barriers that discourage women's full participation in STI, while also highlighting the enablers that can help attract and retain more qualified women in the field.
- The WESTIR project also highlights key recommendations for staff, management and policymakers to help reduce barriers and bridge the gender gap in STI.
- Bridging gender gap in STI is not only a moral obligation but a strategic imperative that strengthens institutional capacity for excellence in research, innovation, and industrial development.

Executive Summary

Ghana's research institutions play a pivotal role in advancing national development through scientific inquiry, innovation, and industrial applications. Among them, the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the Ghana Atomic Energy Commission (GAEC) have emerged as leading contributors to the country's research landscape. However, persistent gender disparities within these institutions hinder their capacity to fully leverage human capital and foster inclusive scientific progress. This policy brief is based on insights gathered from a study conducted to understand the nature of systemic barriers and enablers that influence women's participation in Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) research and regulatory activities focusing on CSIR, GAEC, the Environmental Protection Authority (EPA) and a private sector entity, Bonstech Sustainability and Management Experts (BONSTECH). The policy brief presents the structural and institutional challenges that impede women's participation and career progression in Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI), and outlines practical recommendations for addressing these barriers while embedding key enablers such as mentorship and capacity development.

Introduction

Gender disparity persists in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) careers and particularly in research with women constituting just 30% of researchers worldwide (UIS, 2019). Several interventions have been implemented over the years focusing on mentorship, capacity development and policies, among others. For example, the gender policy of the EPA has the vision to ensure gender balance in recruitment, placement, promotions and career development of staff. Also, the goal of the CSIR gender policy is to mainstream gender equality and women's empowerment concerns into the CSIR Governing Council's process to improve equitability in staff employment, further training, promotions, representation on committees and programmes, and other social engagements.

Notwithstanding, women continue to face multiple barriers some of which are systemic and can be linked to conditions of service, core labour standards, influence from social networks, and training and skills enhancement opportunities, among others. In Ghana, these barriers have not been adequately identified and interrogated in-depth, hence the project titled 'Women's participation in STI research, capacity building and mentorship programmes: The trends, barriers and enablers (WESTIR)' was developed to identify the barriers and enablers and propose evidenced-based recommendations.

This policy brief presents key findings from the study conducted in two STI-based public research institutions, one public regulatory institution and a private firm. It highlights the major barriers staff in these institutions face, which could impact their career progression as well as the enablers that promote staff retention and job satisfaction. Targeted recommendations are proposed for staff, management of the institutions and policy makers.

Barriers affecting effective participation in STI research and regulatory activities

This section examines barriers related to job quality including perceptions about current job, working conditions and compensation, occupational health and safety (OHS), social protection, training and skills development, access to working facilities and technology, and other issues related to core labour standards.

Perceptions about current Job

Both women and men researchers and regulators reported overall lower job satisfaction with as many as 60-69% of staff across the three public institutions dissatisfied with their current jobs. The major issues accounting for the overall low job satisfaction were low remuneration, poor working facilities, high income tax relative to basic salary, and inconsistent promotion criteria. Other reasons provided mainly by women were limited leadership opportunities, lack of recognition, and exclusion from impactful projects.

Working Conditions and Compensation

Overloaded work schedule, insufficient remuneration, and limited family-supportive policies significantly constrain women's sustained participation in STI careers within research and regulatory institutions. Given their predominant role as primary caregivers, women with family responsibilities face considerable challenges, especially when the pursuit of advanced studies necessitates prolonged separation from their households.

Occupational Health and Safety (OHS)

Gender-neutral occupational health and safety (OHS) protocols often overlook the distinct safety requirements of women working in laboratories, field settings, and industrial research environments. Respondents identified key health concerns including back pain caused by inappropriate furniture, exposure to hazardous chemicals, and vision issues resulting from prolonged screen time. Another issue of concern to some women is the poor quality and maintenance of restrooms and sanitation facilities in some institutions that potentially affect women's reproductive and general health conditions.

Social Protection

Inadequate maternity provisions, limited access to childcare support, and the absence of robust mechanisms for addressing various forms of harassment continue to undermine inclusiveness within the research institutions. According to the respondents who had been victims of gender-based violence, this often occurred in the form of offensive language by male colleagues and instances of inappropriate touching. While a few male respondents also reported occasional unwelcome advances from female colleagues and concerns about the provocative dressing by some female staff, the prevalence and severity of issues reported by women were notably higher.

A major barrier to addressing harassment is the lack of trust in institutional structures. Many women are discouraged from reporting incidents due to unclear reporting procedures, limited peer support, and male-dominated leadership, where decision-makers are often perceived to protect or defend their male counterparts who indulge in these harassments. Respondents noted that reporting was further deterred by fear of stigmatization and victimization and a belief that complaints would not be taken seriously. Among those who did report, majority indicated that no meaningful action was taken by management, reinforcing a culture of silence and impunity.

Training and Skills Development

Female staff frequently face limited access to advanced training, fellowships, and leadership development opportunities essential for career advancement. Notably, 69% of respondents reported never having participated in a mentorship programme. While there was no significant gender-based differences in mentorship participation, statistical differences were observed across institutions. Additionally, engagement in women-specific fellowships, awards, and grants such as African Women in Agricultural Research and Development (AWARD) and Organization for Women in Science for the Developing World (OWSD) fellowships was relatively low compared to general opportunities.

Access to Laboratories, Equipment, Facilities, and Technology

Unequal access to well-resourced laboratories and research tools limits women's capacity to deliver high-impact scientific work. Results from the WESTIR study showed that both women and men are equally affected by limited access to equipment, laboratory facilities and other tools that will facilitate their work. Except for Bonstech where staff reported adequate access to the required equipment, as many as 74% of staff in CSIR, 66% in EPA and 81% in GAEC had limited or no

access. Additionally, many respondents indicated a lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) and safety gear that are necessary for safe operations in the field and laboratories. Another concern was the lack of vehicles for fieldwork and transportation, which is essential for conducting research and outreach activities effectively.

Core Labour Standards

Core labour standards, also known as fundamental principles and rights at work aim to protect basic human rights in the workplace and ensure decent work for all. The rights to protect people against discrimination and intimidation at work were often violated in the form of bullying by superiors, inappropriate comments and accusations, and exclusion and sidelining. Discrimination and intimidation, which are also related to gender-based violence, were reportedly higher in EPA where 43% of women and only 8% of men had been discriminated against in various ways. The equivalent percentages in CSIR were 22% for women and 17.3% for men and in GAEC (20% for women, 25% for men). A few respondents also reported discrimination based on their backgrounds and ethnicities. Gender disparities persist in contract conditions, recruitment practices, and representation in decision-making bodies within the three public institutions.

The Enablers influencing women's participation in science and research

The main enablers reported were job stability and flexibility, high level of collaboration with colleagues, and opportunities for capacity development; with 25% of respondents across the four institutions currently on study leave. Enablers such as targeted capacity-building programmes, institutional support mechanisms, and active mentorship networks were found to facilitate women's career progression. Additional enablers included encouragement and emotional support from social networks such as workplace colleagues, spouses, and children. Potential enablers were alignment between the job and one's programme of study and career goals, a gender-sensitive work environment, access to more funded projects, and better incentives.

Mentorship is essential for building confidence, fostering leadership, and improving retention of women in STI. At the institutional level, responses from EPA highlight a significant gap in staff's participation in mentorship programmes. The few mentorship programmes mentioned were mostly external and varied in structure and impact. On the other hand, in-house mentorship programme was common among CSIR respondents - both male and females - with a good number also citing

external mentoring programmes which are mainly in the form of fellowships they participated in. Internal mentorship programmes are often aligned to the specific goals and needs of an institution, which is crucial for women to develop skills that directly apply to their roles.

Although just about 31% of respondents had participated in mentorship programmes, the benefits reported are encouraging. The mentorship, among others, supported the beneficiaries in personal development, building their confidence level, knowledge acquisition, enhancing research and technical skills, and professional exposure and development. The mentorships were effective largely because of availability of logistics and adequate funding, supportive mentors, support from management, and good content of the mentoring programmes. In one case, a female mentee was sponsored to join the programme with her breastfeeding infant. The mentorship programmes also provided opportunities for career guidance, knowledge sharing, networking, contributing to problem solving and making societal impacts.

The main challenge women experienced in the mentorship programmes, especially the non-residential ones, were the limited time and short duration of the programmes making it necessary to work under pressure to deliver all assignments while combining that with home responsibilities. A few beneficiaries could not complete the mentorship programmes due to constrained work-life balance.

Conclusion

Advancing gender equity within research institutions is not only a moral obligation but a strategic imperative that strengthens institutional capacity for excellence in research, innovation, and industrial development. By dismantling systemic barriers and institutionalizing mentorship and capacity-building initiatives, organizations such as CSIR, GAEC, EPA and BONSTECH could serve as national benchmarks for inclusive leadership in STI careers.

Recommendations and Policy Actions

A) Recommendations for Staff

1. Promote Gender-Responsive Mentorship

- Senior researchers should intentionally mentor early-career female colleagues, offering guidance on research, publication, funding, and career progression.

- Establish peer support and learning circles to help build confidence, leadership skills, and a sense of belonging.

2. Advocate for Gender-Inclusive Work Environments:

- Encourage management to implement flexible working arrangements (e.g., adjusted hours, remote options) to accommodate family responsibilities.
- Support the creation of lactation rooms, childcare facilities, or partnerships with daycare providers where feasible.

3. Challenge Gender Bias and Stereotypes:

- Call out and discourage the use of gendered language, biased assumptions, or discriminatory behaviour during meetings, peer reviews, and evaluations.
- Participate in unconscious bias and gender-sensitivity training offered by the institution.

4. Encourage and Support Women's Participation in Leadership:

- a. Nominate or recommend qualified women for leadership roles, conference panels, and decision-making committees.
- b. Ensure women's voices are heard and respected in collaborative research and administrative discussions.

5. Support the Reporting and Redress of Harassment:

- Be an ally: offer support to colleagues who report sexual harassment or gender discrimination.
- Uphold confidentiality and encourage a safe and non-judgmental environment for disclosures.
- Familiarize yourself with the institution's harassment reporting mechanisms and encourage their fair use.

6. Contribute to Sex-Disaggregated Data Collection:

- Ensure research and institutional reports include data disaggregated by sex.
- Use this data to monitor gender trends in staffing, publications, grants, and promotions.

7. Champion Institutional Gender Policies:

- Engage with and provide input into the development and implementation of institutional gender equity policies.
- Participate in gender equity committees or working groups if available.

8. Ensure Equal Access to Research Opportunities:

- a. Transparently share information on grant calls, fellowships, training, and travel opportunities with all colleagues.
- b. Support women researchers in preparing competitive grant applications and connecting with networks.

B. Recommendations for Management of Institutions

1. Establish Dedicated Research Grants for Women Scientists: Allocate a fixed proportion of national research funds to early- and mid-career women-led projects.

2. Mandate Gender Equity Plans in Grant Applications: Require all institutions seeking research funding to submit a gender action plan.

3. Institutionalize Sex-Disaggregated Data Collection: Systematically collect, analyse, and publish gender-specific data on grant applications, review outcomes, and awardees.

4. Invest in Leadership and Mentorship Programs: Support training and coaching programs to prepare women for leadership roles in science and research governance.

5. Create a Gender Advisory Panel: Form a committee to advise councils on gender mainstreaming, monitoring, and policy development.

6. Improve Job Satisfaction and Recognition

- Institutionalize gender-inclusive awards and career progression frameworks.
- Include women in strategic projects and research leadership roles.

7. Promote Fair Working Conditions and Compensation

- Conduct gender pay audits and adjust disparities.
- Introduce flexible working hours, remote work options, and return-to-work

programs for new mothers.

8. Strengthen Gender-Responsive OHS

- Review OHS standards to include gender-specific risks.
- Provide gender-appropriate PPE and safety training.

9. Capacity Building and Mentorship:

- Launch formal mentorship programs across all institutes of CSIR, GAEC, EPA and Bonstech
- Encourage intergenerational and cross-disciplinary mentorship structures.
- Offer regular gender-responsive training in digital tools, innovation management, grant writing, and science communication.
- Establish links with international networks to expose women scientists to global STI platforms

C. Recommendations for Policy Makers

1. Institutionalize Gender Equity in STI Policy Frameworks

- Integrate gender equality as a core principle in national STI and research policies.
- Mandate gender equity considerations in institutional accreditation, funding eligibility, and performance reviews.

2. Establish Dedicated Funding for Women in Research

- Create targeted grants, fellowships, and research chairs for women, particularly in male-dominated STEM fields.
- Provide re-entry grants for women returning to research careers after caregiving breaks.

3. Mandate Gender Equity Plans for Research Institutions

- Require all publicly funded research institutions and universities to develop, implement, and report on gender equity action plans.
- Include clear benchmarks on recruitment, promotion, leadership, and retention of women in research.

4. Invest in Gender-Responsive Capacity Building

- Fund nationwide mentorship and leadership development programmes tailored to women in STI.
- Support institutions like CSIR, GAEC, and universities to establish structured mentorship and professional development pipelines for women.

5. Strengthen Legal and Institutional Mechanisms to Address Harassment

- Enforce mandatory anti-sexual harassment policies and grievance redress mechanisms in all research and tertiary institutions.
- Monitor compliance and hold institutions accountable through independent oversight bodies.

6. Support the Establishment of Family-Friendly Policies

- Incentivize research institutions to adopt family-friendly policies such as paid maternity leave, childcare support, and flexible work arrangements.
- Provide matching funds or subsidies to institutions that implement such support systems.

7. Ensure Robust Data Collection and Monitoring

- Mandate the collection and publication of sex-disaggregated data on research funding, staffing, and performance.
- Use this data to inform policy design and resource allocation.

8. Promote Public Awareness and Gender Norm Shifting

- Launch national campaigns to challenge patriarchal norms that discourage women's participation in science.
- Celebrate successful women in STI as role models through media and public awards.

9. Strengthen Collaboration with Civil Society and Gender Advocacy Groups

- Work with organizations such as Women in Science, Women in Nuclear Ghana (WiN-Ghana), and African Women in Agricultural Research and Development (AWARD) to align national policy with grassroots realities.

- Support networking platforms for women researchers to build community and visibility.

10. Appoint Gender Focal Persons in Key STI Institutions

- Designate and train Gender Focal Persons within research ministries and councils to guide inclusive decision-making.
- Ensure representation of women on all national research and STI advisory bodies.

11. Promote Fair Working Conditions and Compensation

- Conduct gender pay audits and adjust disparities.

12. Enforce and Monitor Core Labour Standards

- Strengthen policies on fair recruitment, anti-discrimination, and gender-balanced decision-making.
- Set targets for women's representation in senior management and scientific committees.
- Introduce flexible working hours, remote work options, and return-to-work programs for new mothers.

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